

The publishing house and the library

Knowledge circulation at a crossroads

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Scientific knowledge is circulated through readers and authors. Libraries served the first, publishers the second. It was that way for centuries, but will it remain so after 1991, the year of the birth of the World Wide Web?

The ones who, without a doubt, have gotten away with the best in the digital revolution of academic publishing are the great classic publishers. Over the past decades, they have steered their companies through sometimes turbulent waters, with income increasing annually and maintaining generous profit margins. They were able to digitize the business processes without having to change their essence. Open science can herald a new heyday for them. Are we heading for an oligopoly?

Libraries have suffered damage. Their core functions have virtually disappeared, except at the cultural heritage libraries. Only management of study rooms, information provision and contract management have remained. However, their future will depend on the ability to collectively build a global knowledge network, based on their repositories, treasure troves of publications and research data. But then they have to be integrated into a larger whole, both organizationally and technically. Is that going to work?

Institutions that feel responsible not only for their research, but also for the way in which the results find their way to society cannot ignore these questions.

Own library

Traditionally, every university had its own library – in the Netherlands required by law until 1980 – which built up a scientific collection and made it accessible through card catalogues. In the 1960s, the first non-paper sources of information emerged. Large files of excerpts from published papers, such as Chemical Abstracts, Biological Abstracts and Medline, became searchable both via telephone connections and later from CD, with the results visible on small monitors with green matrix letters. The articles themselves were then copied from the library's paper journal collection. Not long after, libraries began digitizing their own catalogs; often jointly, as in the Dutch Central Catalogue. Then, when the publishers started supplying these metadata, the cataloging departments disappeared from the libraries, first for journals, later also for books.

The World Wide Web came into existence in 1991. Users got direct access to the available digital information, which grew exponentially. Through arXiv, physicists made the author's version of their articles public before submitting them to a publisher for publication. This meant a considerable acceleration in the knowledge circulation. Only much later would other disciplines follow this approach.

Competition between publishers was lacking. Each publisher was the sole owner of the copyright and thus had a monopoly in determining the conditions for access to the published documents. Through mergers and acquisitions, a small number of large publishers had established themselves at the top of the journal market. For these publishers, annual price increases of up to 10 percent and profit margins of 35 to 40 percent were the rule; Elsevier publishing house symbolized this development. Libraries could not keep up with the price

increases. The purchase of books dropped drastically and they could no longer maintain subscriptions. Because the major publishers wanted to maintain their income anyway, they decided to increase prices accordingly. This started a vicious circle that became known as the serials crisis.

In 2001, Elsevier was the first major publisher to break through this downward spiral with the move to the big deal. This meant that each library would continue to pay for its own package of subscriptions, but would now have digital access to all Elsevier journals. The publisher would thereby reduce the annual price increase by half. The business operations thus remained intact. Although the publisher's income rose less rapidly than before, this was offset by simpler administration. The big deals provided a breathing space, without changing anything in the system. A bizarre side effect was that libraries started paying completely different amounts for the same product. Price comparisons were, however, impossible due to confidentiality clauses in the contracts.

The consequences lay elsewhere. First of all, digitization made it unnecessary to bind the journals and store them in stacks. Over time, a separate administrative industry had emerged to keep track of which libraries had subscribed to which journals: the journal agent, with names such as Swets & Zeitlinger, Blackwells and Faxon. The big deals also made them redundant. The work of reference librarians was the core function of a library; they selected the journals and books that libraries would include in the collection. With the package deals, this function first disappeared for journals and later, when publishers also started offering books in a package, almost completely. Finally, the classic university librarian, a highly educated gentleman, had to make way for a change manager (she/he).

Readers meanwhile made the switch en masse to Google Scholar, which from 2004 offered access to 'everything', except paper books and articles from subscription journals. Google Books, a global scanning project, has since made millions of books digitally accessible. The project is still ongoing and enables major libraries to make their special collections available online. Articles from subscription journals remained locked behind a paywall of 25 euros per article for non-subscribers.

[Share for free](#)

To break the paywall, ResearchGate started a platform in 2007 that allows its members (now 20 million scientists) to share their publications with each other for free. The site does not wish to exercise any control over copyright, publishers believe that it should. Lawsuits are still pending.

[Pirate site](#)

Sci-Hub is currently the most controversial project in its field. The pirate site gives free and unlimited access to articles and books (now 88 million). Subscription publishers have filed and won lawsuits against Sci-Hub. The site then continues under a different address.

[Mighty tool](#)

For authors, the computer had gradually become a powerful tool for writing articles and books, but little changed in the publishing process as such. As soon as a publisher agreed in principle to publish a manuscript, the author transferred their copyright and the publisher

got to work. The latter sought peer reviewers who gave a critical assessment of the written material, generally resulting in one or more revisions. The process was double blind, ie the writer and peer reviewers did not know each other, their dialogue was conducted through an editor appointed by the publisher. Both the editors and the peer reviewers were scientific volunteers. In the end, an accepted version was created. Turnaround times from six months to more than a year were not uncommon. After a finishing touch, the publication followed and the sale started; articles bundled in journals, books one by one. Libraries paid for their journal subscriptions in advance, books were bought on order. Scientific bookshops also bought books. Article authors were not paid at all, sometimes book authors received a modest royalty.

The copyright owner, in this case the publisher, determined the conditions for the publications to be put into circulation, such as the price and the permitted reuse. For example, a writer needed permission, and sometimes had to pay, to include their own article in study material, publish it in another language, or post it on their own website. It was enshrined in the law though that anyone could copy small parts from a work 'for their own practice, study or use', the so-called fair use clause.

While publishers and libraries concluded their first big deals, the academic community formulated a number of 'declarations of independence': the Budapest Open Access Initiative (2002), the Bethesda Statement on Open Access Publishing (2003) and the Berlin Declaration on Open Access to Knowledge in the Sciences and Humanities (2003), with the core that from now on scientific publications should be circulated immediately and freely. The business model of publishers had to be overhauled; their revenue model would no longer be based on the exploitation of copyrights, but on the provision of services. Copyright should remain with (the institution of) the author.

First of all, the academic community thus declared itself indebted to the public domain. This is where the results of publicly funded scientific research belong. Free access to knowledge is vital for a democratic society. New insights must be available worldwide – in the northern and southern hemispheres – for science, education and the knowledge-intensive professions. Citizen scientists, citizens who are actively involved in science, underline this development. "Ivory Tower Science" went from a pleonasm to an oxymoron.

Scientific publishing should also become cheaper in this way. It was expected that the monopoly position of publishers would give way to a model in which publishers would compete with each other in the provision of publishing services, such as organizing peer review, editing, laying out, publishing on a website, registration and long-term storage.

Indeed, shortly after the big declarations, the first open access publishers appeared, such as BioMed Central and the Public Library of Science. But the percentage of open access publications only grew by 1 percent per year until well into this century. For authors, publishing in the classic journals remained much more attractive. It was still free for them, the procedure was simple and traditional publishers permanently sowed doubts about the quality and viability of the new journals. Studies showing that publishing in open access led to more citations were systematically undermined.

But the main obstacle was the journal impact factor (JIF), the average number of times an article in a journal is cited by others. Files such as Web of Science and Scopus keep track of this. The scores can range from 0 to over 40 for glossy journals such as *Nature*, *Science*, *Cell* or *The Lancet*. Managers and research funders conveniently used this average, which is also

notorious for its manipulability, as a measure of the quality of an individual scientist and his research. Authors therefore tried to get their articles published in journals with the highest journal impact factor. And those were still the classic subscription journals.

Open access also offers opportunities to cheaters, the predatory journals. Articles submitted by authors to these journals are, after payment of a publication fee of up to 1000 euros, immediately available on the internet without any changes. These 'publications' then take on a life of their own and undermine confidence in science. So far no answer has been found, all the more so as these predatory journals are increasingly successful in mimicking respectable journals. After all, the reference librarians, who once selected journals on the basis of quality, have disappeared.

Diamond journal

The complete counterpart of the predatory journals are the diamond journals, small open access journals published by universities, research institutes, learned societies or research funds. Publishing therein is free, because the issuer bears the costs. Multilingualism also flourishes in this corner of the open access culture: Spanish, Portuguese, French, Indonesian. It is estimated that there are about 25,000 of these journals, most of them in the Southern Hemisphere. The Action Plan for Diamond Open Access that has just been launched by Science Europe, among others, is committed to rolling out this model worldwide.

In 2018, a number of large research funders united in cOAlition S, with the aim of making open access publishing mandatory as a condition for project funding from 2021. This was of course no problem for articles in open access journals. From 2020, cOAlition S will recognize so-called transformative arrangements for subscription journals. With those arrangements, libraries commit themselves to continue to pay the same amount as before, with an indexation of 2 to 3 percent. Articles by authors of the contracted institutions are then published in open access, next to the subscription articles, in hybrid journals. The underlying publication system thus remains intact, just as it was with the big deals eighteen years earlier. Publishing, whether or not in open access, remains free for authors; the publishers have once again assured themselves of growing income each year in advance. The bizarre price differences from the big deals now result in an institution-dependent publication price per article. Freedom of Information procedures in several countries broke the confidentiality clauses, and there appears to be no competition.

An ongoing point of contention concerns the rights to an article accepted for publication by a subscription publisher. cOAlition S states in its Rights Retention Strategy that this version is still in the public domain. After all, it is the work of the author(s) and the peer reviewers, employed by public institutions. Publishers believe that organizing the peer review process is an essential step from which they can derive rights. Authors get stuck in this: if they meet the requirements of their financier, the publisher can refuse to publish the article; if they follow the publisher, this may have consequences for the financing of their project.

Peer Community in

A new initiative may provide a solution to this rights issue. Peer Community in (PCI) has set up peer review groups for – now fifteen – different disciplines. An author can submit their article to such a group. After a thorough peer review, if the assessment is positive, the

(revised) article with the peer reviews will be made public. This puts an accepted version of the article in the public domain. The writer is then free to publish the article in the Peer Community Journal (a diamond journal), or to submit it to another journal. A growing number of journals accept these articles, whether or not on the basis of their own peer review. PCI is part of a new development in which the academic community itself is taking on the peer review process as a separate service.

Resistance to the journal impact factor as the dominant factor in career decisions for scientists was given a voice in the 2012 San Francisco Declaration on Research Assessment (DORA), which received widespread international resonance (signed by 2,500 organizations and 19,000 scientists). The statement calls for the factor to be no longer used as a measure of the quality of scientists or their research and offers suggestions for other assessment criteria.

The Dutch academic community is joining this with the national program 'Recognition and appreciation'. The program also has an impact on the choice of journals in which scientists publish. Aspects other than the journal impact factor may now play a role, such as the openness of the journal, its distribution and diversity, the design and the quality of the peer review (open or closed, single blind or double blind, before or after publication, set up by a commercial party or from within the academic community), the speed of publication and the appreciation of colleagues. There are already bottom-up initiatives that map these aspects, but their fragmentation does not yet make large-scale use attractive.

[Journal Observatory](#)

The Center for Science and Technology Studies (CWTS) of Leiden University has taken the initiative to present a number of these initiatives next year on a common platform: the Journal Observatory. Writers can then go 'shopping' there, looking for a suitable magazine to publish in.

[Call for open science](#)

Especially after the Second World War, the impact of science on society increased sharply, but they remained separate worlds, with society as the recipient of scientific results. The Berlin Declaration of 2003 broke that paradigm by declaring scientific research part of the public domain. It is true that open access publishing as such got off to a slow start, but the socialization of science was unstoppable. The call for open science became louder and louder. The entire research process should become transparent: from the project proposal via research design, laboratory logs, clinical trials, data and code used, reports, dissertations, successive article versions and peer reviews to evaluation and valorisation. Science journalists, bloggers, layman's summaries, open days and webinars provide more and more insight into the latest developments.

A key role is played by the so-called repositories, digital archives at university libraries or globally per discipline. Here you can store and make everything accessible almost unlimitedly. Aggregation sites such as Open Access Button and Unpaywall aggregate the metadata from these repositories and contain data on tens of millions of text and data files. With smart software it is possible to distil trends from this and make connections between disciplines visible. Policy makers include these outcomes in their strategic analyses and choices.

However, the reliability of the results of specific searches in such collections leaves something to be desired. Varying document versions, unknown reuse rights, articles from predatory magazines, missing documentation in data collections: it all occurs. Every now and then one manages to find an author and contact them. Universal application of standards and persistent identifiers should improve this, starting with the Digital Object Identifier (DOI) for files, the Open Researcher and Contributor Identifier (ORCID) for scientists, the Research Organization Registry Identifier (ROR ID) for research organizations and CC -BY licenses for reuse information. Crossref, an open community of currently fifteen thousand organizations, has set up a data infrastructure for this. With its help, repositories can develop into nodes in a knowledge semantic web. But the necessary organization is still pending.

The major publishers have also embraced open science. Through acquisitions of successful new initiatives, through mergers or through their own developments, they – Elsevier in the lead, followed by Wiley, Taylor & Francis and SpringerNature – have expanded their range of services, aimed at supporting the entire chain of proposal, research, publication and evaluation. The biggest competitor of Elsevier in this field is Clarivate, itself not a publisher, but owner of Web of Science, among others. These players integrate the separate services, which improves their efficiency and user-friendliness. It gives them insight into the underlying processes and data. Based on this, they can then provide services such as identifying experts, mapping research networks, monitoring funding opportunities, tracing literature use, evaluating and validating research or providing institute reputation analyses. The academic world is watching this development with mixed feelings and is concerned about the information position these dominant publishers are thus building, and their use of it. Control over research data, often part of publications, is a hot topic. In addition, newcomers, as well as existing university presses and societies, are increasingly confronted with a leeway that can no longer be caught up and the choice to stop or be taken over.

Far-reaching consequences

The invention of printing in 1455 by Johann Gutenberg and the invention of the world wide web in 1991 by Tim Berners-Lee have often been compared when it comes to making knowledge accessible. Both events marked a breakthrough with far-reaching social consequences. The printing press led to the disappearance of monastic libraries and their scriptoriums as sources of knowledge, to make way for university libraries and publishers. The world wide web is now lifting the dividing line between the latter two. Will the libraries disappear and the circulation of academic knowledge become a private business? Or will circulating the results of scientific research become part of the public domain? Although the academic world embraces this vision, a joint design is still lacking.

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